

Deliverable D2.2

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Project Acronym:	BioMedBridges	
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Deliverable title:	Definition and segmentation of stakeholders	
WP No.	2	
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WP Title	Outreach and inreach	
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1 Executive summary

- The success of BioMedBridges will depend on outreach and inreach to diverse groups of stakeholders.
- This deliverable describes the use of a survey to define the broad stakeholder groups with whom BioMedBridges needs to engage, and to collect information on how the individual ESFRI-BMS RIs currently engage with these groups.
- We wanted to know who these stakeholders are, how the RIs are currently engaging with them, and what aspects of BioMedBridges the respondents felt we should be consulting this group of stakeholders on.
- Here we report on a preliminary analysis of the survey results and on what our next steps will be.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Ensure the promotion and dissemination of BioMedBridges deliverables to its stakeholders	X	
2	Specify the expectations, motivations and requirements of stakeholders and their inter-relationships with the BMS infrastructures concerning the implementation of common solutions.	X	
3	Involve the stakeholders, including end users, patient organizations and industrial stakeholders, in informing the	X	

	outcome of the BioMedBridges deliverables.		
4	Provide strategic outreach to other projects and relevant initiatives (including the individual BMS RIs and e-Infrastructures, relevant IMI projects and EMBL-EBI Industry Programme) to support the implementation of the common solutions developed by BioMedBridges.	X	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

The goal of BioMedBridges is to make it easier for basic, translational and clinical researchers to work with the data bridges and access huge amounts of biomedical data with the aim to use these data to make discoveries that will enhance the health of European citizens. BioMedBridges is an ambitious and complex project, the success of which will depend on outreach to a diverse group of stakeholders. These range from bench researchers through software developers to biomedical researchers at all stages of the medicines research and development pipeline. Definition of these groups, and identification of appropriate strategies for engaging and training with each group in a targeted way, will be key to the success of the project. This deliverable describes the use of a survey to define the broad stakeholder groups with whom BioMedBridges needs to engage, and to collect information on how the individual ESFRI-BMS RIs currently engage with these groups.

3.2 Definition and segmentation of stakeholders

3.2.1 Purpose of the survey

The purpose of our survey was:

- To define BioMedBridges' stakeholders as a first step towards developing a communication strategy

- To use information on internal stakeholders to develop a plan for inreach to the BioMedBridges partners and to their collaborators in the BMS RIs
- To use information on end-users to inform user centred design of the BioMedBridges services (see D2.3)
- To use information on other external stakeholders to develop an outreach plan for the second half of BioMedBridges

The survey was aimed at representatives from each of the EFRI-BMS RIs involved in BioMedBridges. Our goal was to derive one representative set of responses for each RI. We focused on three broad groups of stakeholder, and asked a consistent set of questions concerning each of these:

Internal stakeholders: those directly involved in coordinating the construction of the RIs and in their future operation.

End users: those who will make use of the infrastructures to enable their research.

Other external stakeholders: those who have an interest in the emerging research infrastructures and can influence their future success.

We wanted to know who these stakeholders are, how the RIs are currently engaging with them, and what aspects of BioMedBridges the respondents felt we should be consulting this group of stakeholders on. The survey was built in SurveyMonkey, an online tool for designing, collecting and analysing surveys. A link to the survey was sent by email to our contacts in each of the research infrastructures. A printable version of the survey is provided in Annex 1.

3.2.2 Analysis of results

Q1: Who are you?

Our original intention was that a single representative would respond to the survey on behalf of each of the research infrastructures. Whilst we did get an answer from each, some research infrastructures provided more than one response and this may bias our preliminary analysis of stakeholder groups somewhat. However, some stakeholder groups are so clearly a high priority

that we do not feel that this will confound our immediate plans for outreach and inreach.

Figure 1: number of respondents from each of the ESFRI-BMS research infrastructures participating in BioMedBridges.

Q2: Within your particular research infrastructure, who are your internal stakeholders?

Eight respondents answered this question. Responses varied enormously in their granularity and in the extent to which they applied to a specific research infrastructure. To add some consistency, and to facilitate discussions on internal stakeholders overlooked by the survey respondents, we have used the results to build a ‘mini ontology’ of internal stakeholders. Several of the responses would benefit from more exploration, and this will be incorporated into the next stage of our analysis.

Level 1 descriptor	Level 2 descriptor	Response to Q2
Industry	Biotech companies	Biotech
Research institutes	Academic research institutes	Coastal marine biological research institutes
Sample collections		Culture collections of marine organisms
Data collections		Data centres focused on marine bioinformatics
Research Infrastructure governance		EATRIS office Amsterdam
Research Infrastructure governance		ECRIN coordination
Research		ECRIN Network Committee

Infrastructure governance		
Research Infrastructure advisors		ECRIN Scientific Board
Research Infrastructure operations		ECRIN Working group members
Funders	Funders at international level	EU correspondents
Funders	Funders at international level	European Commission (in case of EC funding for RI activities)
Funders		funders (ministries, funding agencies, institutional funders) – need to separate funders on European level from funders on national level, private funders (e.g. industry), etc.
	Funders at national level	Funding bodies from ELIXIR countries (national funders)
Funders		Funding organizations
Research institutes	Academic research institutes	Genomics institutes
Hospitals		Hospitals
Industry		Industry
Research Infrastructure operations		infrastructure operators and their scientific organizations
Research Institutes	Academic research institutes	International Organisations, e.g. EMBL
Higher education institutes	University departments	Marine biological departments in Universities
Funders	Funders at national level	Member State governments from ELIXIR Countries (national funders)
Research Infrastructure operations		Organisations that will make up the Nodes (bioinformatics providers, supercomputer centres, etc.
Advocacy groups		patient organizations
Industry	Pharmaceutical industry	pharma (need to add other industries e.g. agri-food, fisheries, etc.)
Research Institutes		Research Institutes
Research Institutes		Research institutions
Research institutes		Research organizations
Research networks		Research Partnerships/networks, e.g. Partnership in Structural Biology, Grenoble, France
Research networks		TraIT project (Translational Research IT) CTMM Eindhoven (example of a research network)
Higher education institutes		Universities

Table 1: First attempt at a 'mini ontology' describing internal stakeholders. This will now be fleshed out to provide a fuller picture of our internal stakeholders.

Q3: Do you already have contact with your internal stakeholders?

Ten respondents answered yes to this question; seven declined to answer and no-one answered 'no'.

Q4: If yes, what kind of contact?

Respondents were asked to select checkboxes for each of the methods that they used to contact their internal stakeholders, and to specify any other methods using a free-text box. The results are summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Methods used by the ESFRI-BMS research infrastructures to contact their internal stakeholders. Other methods included document sharing, websites, newsletters and mailing lists for press releases.

Q5: What aspects of BioMedBridges do you feel we need to consult the internal stakeholders on?

Eight respondents answered this question and their responses are provided below. We have categorised each type of response as a first step towards prioritizing areas for consultation.

Type of response	Response to Q5
Collaboration and community building	Community building with entire EATRIS network
Data and services provided by RIs	Data provided (RI operators)
Standards already used by RIs	Development and harmonisation of standards and ontologies across the domains represented in the BMS RIs
SOPs for data security	Development and implementation of protocols to ensure secure and appropriate access to heterogeneous data types across BMS RIs
Data and services needed by RIs	e-infrastructure construction standards across BMS RIs
How to implement BMB's goals	Harmonisation [of methods for accessing data?]
How to implement BMB's goals	[How to?] implement a federated access system to the diverse data sources across BMS RIs
International aspects of data exchange	International aspects of data exchange
Data and services needed by RIs	Kinds of data and services needed for clinical trials in ECRIN
International aspects of data	Material transfer agreement [need clarity on how this applies to BMB]

exchange	
Data and services needed by RIs	Needs for (imaging) data interoperability
Needs for data security	Needs for data security
Needs for ethics in data management	Needs for ethics in data management
How to implement BMB's goals	Objectives and development of BMB
Data access/exchange policy (?)	Policy [as regards data access?]
Data access/exchange policy (?)	Regulatory and ethical national requirements for data and service exchange for clinical trials in ECRIN
Data and services provided by RIs	Services provided (RI operators)
Sharing best practices	Sharing best practices (tools, data, applications)
Sharing best practices	SOPs
Standards already used by RIs (?)	Standards
How RIs will deploy BMB's products	The direct linkages between ELIXIR and BMB - this could be the scientific and technical deployment of the project
Data and services needed by RIs	What data would be of benefit if made available from other BMS projects
Data and services needed by RIs	What form and volume of data should be accommodated
Data and services needed by RIs	Which key growth points in data generation and consumption can BMB help address

Table 2: Responses to Q5: what aspects of BioMedBridges do you feel we should consult internal stakeholders on? In this context, internal means internal to the BMS RIs. An initial attempt has been made to categorise responses into different groups.

The categories in Table 2 have been used to visually represent the different areas on which we might consult internal stakeholders (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Tag cloud based on frequency of different categories of response to question 5.

Q6: What are the key messages about BioMedBridges that you feel would be important to convey to these stakeholder groups?

This question was intended to explore what we should tell our internal stakeholders, as opposed to what we should ask them about. Eight respondents answered this question and their responses are provided below.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standards and SOPs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The envisioned data bridges will be able to support international ECRIN trials and will enable ECRIN to collaborate more efficiently with EATRIS and BBMRI for joint research projects with the investigative networks for rare diseases, medical devices and nutrition (ECRIN-IA).</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>BMB data bridges may be valuable support to conduct clinical trials in advanced therapies and personalized medicine. - the objective to provide standardised data management and access</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>First of all awareness for the BMB initiative and its objectives</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The added value that BioMedBridges brings to each of the projects involved</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Regular updates on main BMB deliverables</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>BioMedBridges adds value to data and services offered by the BMS RI</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>We strive towards improved interoperability across BMS RIs without enforcing standards</i>

We can categorise these responses into four general themes:

1. Standards and interoperability
2. Facilitating collaboration
3. Adding value to the research infrastructures
4. Raising awareness of BioMedBridges goals and achievements.

Q7: Who are your end users? Group these into broad categories.

Eight respondents answered this question. Responses varied in their granularity and in the extent to which they applied to a specific research infrastructure. To add some consistency, and to facilitate discussions on end users overlooked by the survey respondents, we have used the results to build a 'mini ontology' of internal stakeholders. Several of the responses would benefit from more exploration, and this will be incorporated into the next stage of our analysis.

Type of user	Response to Q7
academic researchers	academic research scientists and students
academic researchers	academic users
academic researchers	biomedical researchers in different fields

clinical investigators	clinical researchers
clinical investigators	human genetics community
pharmaceutical and biotech researchers	Industrial users
pharmaceutical and biotech researchers	industry
pharmaceutical and biotech researchers	Industry
clinical investigators	investigators conducting a clinical trial at the different ECRIN clinical trial centers and clinical research units
large-scale facility strategists	large scale facility strategists
manufacturers	manufacturers
technology developers	technology developers
clinical investigators	medical/clinical users
academic researchers	mouse genetics community
patients	patients
pharmaceutical and biotech researchers	pharma
pharmaceutical and biotech researchers	pharma and biotech industries
policymakers	policymakers
policymakers	policymakers (EC and national)
academic researchers	Principle investigators
students	research students and master students (training and courses)
academic researchers	researchers
study nurses	study nurses
clinical trial managers	trial managers at the clinical trial networks
students	research students and master students (training and courses)
academic researchers	researchers
research infrastructure operators	RI operators (internal services offered by legal entity)
academic researchers	scientists
academic researchers	scientists from the biological sciences
clinical investigators	scientists from the medical sciences
academic researchers	scientists in biology
clinical investigators	scientists in medical sciences
pharmaceutical and biotech researchers	SMEs and industry
translational researchers	translational researchers (both in UMCs and private companies)

Table3: First attempt at a 'mini ontology' describing end users. This will now be fleshed out to provide a fuller picture of our end users.

Q8: Do you already have contact with your end users?

Nine respondents answered yes to this question; eight declined to answer and no-one answered 'no'.

Q9: If yes, what kind of contact?

Eight respondents answered question. Their responses are summarized in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Methods used by the ESFRI-BMS research infrastructures to contact their end users. Other methods included websites, web-based services, e-newsletters, social networks, active participation of end-users in projects, proof-of-concept studies, surveys and user training.

Q10: What aspects of BioMedBridges do you feel we need to consult your future end users on?

Eight respondents answered this question and their responses are provided below. We have categorised each type of response as a first step towards prioritising areas for consultation. We also removed any responses that addressed awareness raising as opposed to consultation. Awareness raising is dealt with in Question 11.

Type of response	Response to Q10
Willingness to share data	are the users prepared to fund [support?] open access?
How to make BMB services comply with good clinical practice/research ethics	Consideration of GCP compliance
How to make BMB services work across national borders	Consideration of national aspects [need more clarity on what is meant by this]
Data and services needed by users	Data processing
Data and services needed by users	Data repositories
Needs for data security	Data security
Needs for data security	Development and implementation of protocols to ensure secure

	and appropriate access to heterogeneous data types
How to make BMB services comply with good clinical practice/research ethics	Ethics policy
How to make BMB services work across different disciplines	Harmonisation [need more clarity on what is meant by this]
How to make BMB services work across different disciplines	harmonization of standards and ontologies across the domains represented in the BMS RIs
How to make BMB services comply with good clinical practice/research ethics	Safeguards for confidentiality of patient data
Willingness to share data	Should data be made publicly available
Data and services needed by users	Standards
Usability	Usability of BMB tools and services
Data and services needed by users	What is the kind of web services they would profit most from?
Willingness to share data	What is the policy on data access?
Needs and practices for data archiving	What is the policy on data preservation?
Data and services needed by users	What priorities they would have for the scientific and technical deployment of ELIXIR and BMB
Data and services needed by users	What their needs are

Table 4: Responses to Q10: what aspects of BioMedBridges do you feel we should consult end users on? In this context, end users means end users of the BMS RIs. An initial attempt has been made to categorise responses into different groups.

The categories in Table 4 have been used to visually represent the different areas on which we might consult internal stakeholders (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Tag cloud based on frequency of different categories of response to question 10.

Q11: What are the key messages about BioMedBridges that you feel would be important to your end users?

Seven respondents answered this question. Their responses are summarised below.

- Keep it **simple**
- BMB should, wherever possible, uphold the principle of **free data access**

- The concept of BMB is too abstract for our end users now; we first have to show **concrete results** and deliverables
- How BioMedBridges brings scientific and technical value; data integration **benefits** the entire research community
- Regular updates on BMB **deliverables**
- BioMedBridges is a stepping stone to **enhance** the scientific services and platforms of the BMS RIs
- This will make your research **easier** by taking out the friction due to possible incomplementarities across BMS RIs

These responses reinforce our plans to prioritise user consultation in the first half of the project, but awareness raising and training in the second half, when we will concrete products to show them.

Q12: Who are your other external stakeholders? Group these into broad categories.

Eight respondents answered this question. Responses varied in their granularity and in the extent to which they applied to a specific research infrastructure. To add some consistency, and to facilitate discussions on external stakeholders overlooked by the survey respondents, we have used the results to build a 'mini ontology' of external stakeholders. Several of the responses would benefit from more exploration, and this will be incorporated into the next stage of our analysis.

Level 1 descriptor	Level 2 descriptor	Response to Q12
Research infrastructure operations	Operators of research infrastructures external to the BMS-RIs	Biobank managers/staff
Researchers	Clinical researchers	Clinical researchers
Researchers	Clinical trial experts	Clinical trial experts
Funders	Commercial funders	Commercial sponsors e.g. Bruker
Regulators	Data protection authorities	Data inspection boards
ELSI experts	Ethical and social experts	Ethical and social experts
ELSI experts	Legal and regulatory experts	Legal and regulatory experts
ELSI experts	Legal and	Experts in regulation

	regulatory experts	
Funders		Funders
Funders		Funding agencies
Funders		Funding bodies and Member States
Public		General public
Media		Media
Industry		Industry
Funders		Institutional funders e.g. Max Planck Society
IT infrastructures	IT departments	IT departments of university medical centers and other (private) partners
Regulators	Data protection authorities	Legal network for patient privacy and other data protection issues
Researchers	Clinical researchers	members of clinical trial networks: F-CRIN, KKSIN, MUW, HECRIN, Molecular Medicine Ireland, KarolinskaInstitutet, ISS,
Policymakers		National and European Policy Makers, EC, ESFRI
Funders	National and regional funders	national funding bodies e.g. MRC, CNRS etc
Funders	National and regional funders	National regional governmental bodies e.g. Regione Toscana
Non-governmental organisations		NGOs
IT infrastructures	National IT infrastructures	Other bio-medical IT infrastructures on a national scale in The Netherlands
Research Infrastructures		Other RI and their representative bodies
Advocacy groups	Patient groups	Patient groups / Associations centred around specific diseases
Researchers		Peers in other European countries
Policymakers		Policy-makers
Funders	National and regional funders	Regional and national government
Policymakers	Policymakers at European level	Related European policy streams (IMI, JPIs, ...)
Funders		research funding experts
Research institutes		Research institutions
Scientific and professional bodies		Research organizations
Industry		SMEs and Industry
Funders	Funders at European level	The European Commission and other relevant institutions
Public		The public
Higher education institutes		Universities and research institutes

Table5: First attempt at a 'mini ontology' describing external stakeholders other than end-users. This will now be fleshed out to provide a fuller picture of our external stakeholders.

Q13: Do you already have contact with these external stakeholders?

Nine respondents answered yes to this question; eight declined to answer and no-one answered 'no'.

Q14: If yes, what kind of contact?

Eight respondents answered this question. Their responses are summarised in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Methods used by the ESFRI-BMS research infrastructures to contact their external stakeholders other than end users. Other methods included websites, newsletters/ mailing lists and surveys.

Q15: What aspects of BioMedBridges do you feel we need to consult them on?

Eight respondents answered this question and their responses are provided below. We have categorised each type of response as a first step towards prioritising areas for consultation.

Type of consultation	Response to Q15
Collaboration and community building	Build European networks of peers
Data and services needed by external stakeholders	Data processing
Data and services needed by external stakeholders	Data repositories
How to make BMB services comply with data protection policies	Data security
How to make BMB services comply with ethics policy	Ethics policy
How to make BMB services comply with European and national laws	Law
How to make BMB services comply with European and	Material transfer agreement [need to seek clarity on what is meant here]
	National differences in research processes, policies, regulatory requirements for data exchange in clinical trials

national laws	
How to make BMB services comply with ethics policy	requirements for the data bridges specific for clinical trials with humans (security? Legal issues?)
Data, services and standards used by external stakeholders	Resources and standards used in ECRIN clinical trial centers and clinical research units
Willingness to share data	should data be made public if IP issues are accommodated
How to make BMB services comply with European and national laws	what is the policy on data access
Willingness to fund open access	would they be willing to fund open access
Potential overlap with other pan-European initiatives	For Member States and the EC, etc, if we consult them it should be on ensuring that there is no unnecessary overlap between BMB and other initiatives that might already be in existence, or finding out how BMB can link in with these other initiatives
How to keep external stakeholders updated on BMB's progress	For the public - if they are to be consulted, it might be best to consult them on how they feel they would like to be kept informed about developments with BMB - ie the frequency, what format it might take, etc.

Table 6: Responses to Q15: what aspects of BioMedBridges do you feel we should consult external stakeholders on? In this context, external stakeholders means stakeholders external to the BMS RIs in addition to end users. An initial attempt has been made to categorise responses into different groups.

Q16: What are the key messages about BioMedBridges that you feel would be important to convey to these stakeholder groups?

Seven respondents answered this question. Their responses are summarised below.

- One for all, all for one
- BioMedBridges will consider ECRIN requirements for the development of data bridges
- Awareness: what relevant activities are going on in the various countries
- Regular update on BMB deliverables (newsletter?)
- BioMedBridges adds value to data and services offered by the BMS RI
- Interoperability reduces friction for the end-users and improves efficiency across the RI landscape, saving time and money.
- For Member States and the EC, then I think the message should be about how BMB brings value to the scientific community and to each of the individual RIs it brings together.

- For the public, the message should be about what concrete benefits they get from the work that BMB does - although this can be a difficult message to convey.

We will incorporate these suggestions into future discussions about our messages to stakeholder groups, and incorporate the outcome of these discussions into the outreach plan for BioMedBridges.

Q17: Please provide contact information (name and e-mail address) for someone who can answer outreach-related questions for your infrastructure

Eight respondents provided contact details for outreach contacts in their infrastructures. We will continue to consult with these contacts and follow up with those research infrastructures who have not yet provided an outreach contact.

3.2.3 Next steps

We thank all those who contributed to the survey. Our next steps will be:

1. To present our analysis to the BioMedBridges technical coordination committee at their November teleconference.
2. To engage with the survey respondents to seek clarity on some of their responses
3. To seek feedback from the survey respondents and other BMB partners on our analysis, especially on our initial categorisation of stakeholders, what we should consult them on, and messages that we should convey to them.
4. To draft a plan for outreach and inreach based on this analysis, and to incorporate relevant stakeholder groups into user centered design of the BioMedBridges services.

4 Publications

N/A

5 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

The delivery is slightly delayed due to a slow start to the project, progress in hiring suitable staff and establishing the necessary communication channels.

6 Adjustments made

The use of resources was adjusted. The deliverable presents a starting point that will be expanded on throughout the duration of the project.

7 Efforts for this deliverable

Institute	Person-months (PM)		Period
	actual	estimated	
1 EMBL-EBI	1 (in-kind)	1	September 2012
5 UDUS	0.2	2	
13 VUMC	0.5	5	
Total	0.7 + 1 (in-kind)		

Background information

This deliverable relates to WP2; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DOW) is included below.

WP2 Title: Outreach and inreach
Lead: Deborah Alfarez (VUMC)
Participants: VUMC

BioMedBridges is an ambitious and complex project, the success of which will depend on outreach to a diverse group of stakeholders. These range from bench researchers, software developers through biomedical researchers at all stages of the medicines research and development pipeline. WP 2 will contribute to the successful implementation of BioMedBridges by coordinating targeted inreach and outreach activities.

Inreach activities will ensure that the BioMedBridges participants share a common vision on the aims of the software solutions implemented by the technical work package. For example, it will ensure that user requirements and user testing scenarios are embedded into the project from the very beginning.

Outreach activities to various stakeholders groups, including software developers, end-users of the BioMedBridges services and Patient groups, will raise awareness of the solutions developed in the technical work packages. Our strategy will include making the most of our links to the individual BMS RIs to communicate with these stakeholder groups on our behalf. BioMedBridges" outreach activities will play a key role in assuring that BioMedBridges is seen as a trustable party (for example, by the patient who has the right to determine who is using his data, or the bench researcher who might need to change aspects of his day-to-day work when using solutions developed by BioMedBridges).

Work package number	WP2	Start date or starting event:	Mo 1
Work package title	Outreach and inreach		
Activity Type	COORD		
Participant number	13: VUMC	1: EMBL	5: UDUS
Person-months per participant:	40	2	2
Objectives			
1. To ensure the promotion and dissemination of BioMedBridges deliverables to its stakeholders.			
2. To specify the expectations, motivations and requirements of stakeholders			

and their inter-relationships with the BMS infrastructures concerning the implementation of common solutions

3. To involve the stakeholders, including end users, patient organizations and industrial stakeholders, in informing the outcome of the BioMedBridges deliverables.
4. To provide strategic outreach to other projects and relevant initiatives (including the individual BMS RIs and e-Infrastructures, relevant IMI projects and EMBL-EBI Industry Programme) to support the implementation of the common solutions developed by BioMedBridges.

Description of work and role of participants

Task 1: Stakeholder definition and stratification (M1-M6)

(Leader: VUMC, Participants: UDUS, EMBL-EBI)

BioMedBridges is an ambitious and complex project, the success of which will depend on outreach to a diverse group of stakeholders. These range from bench researchers, software developers through biomedical researchers, both in academia and in industry, at all stages of the medicines research and development pipeline.

Definition of these groups, and identification of appropriate strategies for engaging and training with each group in a targeted way, will be key to the success of the project. Through consultation with (i) project partners, (ii) the communications teams of the BMS Research infrastructures, (iii) other e-Infrastructure projects (iv) industrial stakeholders e.g. via the IMI project EMTRAIN and (v) our advisory board we will define stakeholders as a first step towards developing a communication strategy. Stakeholder groups can broadly be divided into:

- (1) technical personnel in the BMS-RIs and e-infrastructures;
- (2) end-users of the BMS RIs (ranging from basic researchers through to physicians, other professionals involved in clinical trials and industry representatives);
- (3) patient organisations.

(1) Software developers (EMBL-EBI): sharing of expertise in data integration and software interoperability will be an important part of BioMedBridges, as it brings together developers from diverse application domains with different cultures; for example, the medical informatics, bioinformatics and cheminformatics communities have very different models for the development and implementation of standards. 'Inreach' to the project partners will be an important goal in this respect. We will also need to communicate with technical personnel involved in the BMS RIs but not in this project. Technical personnel in related EU-funded projects, including INFRA-2011-1.2.1: e-Science environments, INFRA-2011-1.2.2: Data infrastructures for e-Science and INFRA-2011-1.1.7. Life sciences bio-molecular data resources and services represent a third target group, of great importance if Europe is to gain maximum benefit from its investment in e-Science infrastructure.

(2) End-users of the BioMedBridges services (EMBL-EBI, VUMC, UDUS). The immediate goal of BioMedBridges is to make it easier for basic, translational

and clinical researchers to work with the data bridges and access huge amounts of biomedical data with the aim to use these data to make discoveries that will enhance the health of European citizens. These users will have to change their everyday workflow at the bench, or in the clinic and are therefore an extremely important target group for engagement. Not only do we need to inform them of new services that will enhance their research capability; we also need to involve them, from an early stage, in the development of these services. Outreach to our users will therefore need to include strategies for user testing.

We will do this by organising a workshop with representatives of the technical work packages during the first year of the project, to agree on a process for user testing and to identify appropriate subjects for user testing.

To ensure that BioMedBridges successfully implements the access to cutting edge e-technology platforms for academia and industry, the end user stakeholders that will be defined and stratified in task 1 and for which an outreach plan will be developed in task 2 will include industrial stakeholders. For this amongst others contacts to IMI Knowledge management projects will be used and if necessary established. In addition in order to reach its target with respect to industrial stakeholders, namely to create an improved environment for translation to industry and commercial exploitation of data a close interaction will be established with WP3 to ensure cross-fertilisation when identifying key industry players in the standardisation arena across the involved disciplines. Patients' Organisations (VUMC, UDUS). BioMedBridges' impact will be seen through expediting research, the ultimate goal of which will be improved health of Europe's citizens, especially in terms of better healthcare and improved treatments. As BioMedBridges will develop architectures for data sharing that will also include sensitive patient data, the involvement of patient organisations will be a crucial factor for the acceptance, dissemination and overall outcome of the project. Because patients must consent to the use of their data and samples for research, the involvement of patient organisations will advance the project's aims to improve data exchange. We will invite an appropriate representative to join the BioMedBridges advisory board and will work with this representative to ensure that BioMedBridges builds trust among all groups involved in BioMedBridges.

Task 2: Creation of inreach and outreach plans (M6-M48)
(Leader: VUMC, Participants: UDUS, EBI)

In this task, we will develop a plan to involve the stakeholders defined in task 1. Again, the involvement of our advisory board members and those of the BMS research infrastructures will be important. The plan will be split into two phases. In years 1 and 2 the focus will be on establishing awareness with stakeholders relevant to WPs 3-5 about BioMedBridges and its goals. These stakeholders include industrial stakeholders as described in task one. The outreach plan to the industrial stakeholders will make use of the link to the IMI Knowledge Management projects as well on the existing EBI/ELIXIR industry programme. The second phase (years 3 & 4) will be based on systematically informing stakeholders about the solutions implemented within BioMedBridges.

Phase 1 will need to include a plan for 'inreach' to the BioMedBridges partners and to their collaborators in the BMS RIs. Each of the partner infrastructures is itself a large and distributed 'organisation' so good communication with these scientists is non-trivial and will require effort and commitment. It will be necessary to raise awareness in these communities of the e-science approach as a new way of working, introducing the ideas of in-silico labs and multi-disciplinary, cross organizational collaboration among all BMS-RIs. This will include establishing a common understanding of the goals and the methods for achieving these goals, at all levels of participants within the BMS-RIs.

Phase 2 will need to include resources for travel to conferences to promote adoption of BioMedBridges standards, best practices and tools, and for publishing the achievements of BioMedBridges in the Scientific, Technical and Medical press. Much of this will be done in the individual infrastructures, and this work package will take steps to ensure that key messages from the project are communicated by the individual BMS RIs. The final AGM of BioMedBridges will be open to all stakeholder groups and will include a programme aimed at celebrating the deployment of robust data bridges and services promoting interoperability between the BMS RIs with all our stakeholders.

Task 3: Development of a BioMedBridges brand and supporting materials (M6-M18)

(Leader: VUMC, Participants:, EMBL-EBI)

We will support the BioMedBridges partners to promote the infrastructures developed by BioMedBridges by managing the development of a logo, PowerPoint and poster templates, key messages, press releases and a regular project bulletin. A BioMedBridges website and newsletter will disseminate the supporting material. We will work closely with the BioMedBridges project manager, who will be responsible for managing the project website, to achieve these goals.

Deliverables

No.	Name	Due month
D2.1	Initial basic branding, including logo, power point and poster templates	2
D2.2	Definition and segmentation of stakeholders	6
D2.3	Definition of user testing process with technical work packages	9
D2.4	Development and implementation of outreach plan for different stakeholder groups	36
D2.5	Final AGM – meeting and report	48